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1.2 DEVELOPMENT AND STUDY OF THE PROPERTIES OF COMPOSITIONS BASED ON DICHLOROPHENYLETHANE MODIFIED TRIPLE ETHYLEN-PROPYLENE RUBBER

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Abstract

Composite materials (composites) are multicomponent materials, usually consisting of a plastic base (matrix) reinforced with fillers with high strength, rigidity, etc. The combination of dissimilar substances leads to the creation of a new material, the properties of which differ quantitatively and qualitatively from the properties of each of its constituents. By varying the composition of the matrix and filler, their ratio, the orientation of the filler, a wide range of materials with the required set of properties is obtained. Many composites are superior to traditional materials and alloys in their mechanical properties and at the same time they are lighter. The use of composites usually makes it possible to reduce the mass of a structure while maintaining or improving its mechanical characteristics. In the presented article, the process of modification of ethylene-propylene rubber (SKEPT-60) with 1.2 dichlorophenylethane, a functional group compound, was carried out. Then, the rheological properties of the mixture of ethylene propylene rubber with 1.2 dichlorophenylethane in the appropriate facilities in the laboratory were studied in the environment of the influence of various factors in the temperature range (100-190) °C. It is proposed to purchase products based on modified ethylene-propylene rubber with temperature, tear resistance and metal bond strength.

Keywords. Ethylene propylene rubber, 1.2 dichlorophenylethane, composition, modification, rheological properties, effective viscosity, strength and elastic properties

Introduction

A composite is any material made from more than one component, so there are many composite materials around us that we use without thinking about whether they belong to the class of composites.

Modern composite materials usually consist of two components: a fiber and a matrix. High-strength glass, carbon, organic, boron and other fibers are used as fibers. The matrix is both thermosetting resins (phenolic, epoxy, polyester, etc.) and thermoplastic polymers (polyamides, polyethylene, polystyrene, etc.). These materials have sufficiently high strength, low thermal conductivity, high electrical insulating properties, in addition, they are transparent to radio waves.

The matrix in composite materials ensures the solidity of the material, the transfer and distribution of stress in the filler, determines heat, moisture, fire and chemical resistance. Reinforcing fillers in the form of thin fibers, threads, bundles or fabrics perceive the main share of the load of composites and provide the physical and mechanical characteristics of the material, in particular, high strength and rigidity in the direction of fiber orientation. The composition may also include thickeners, pigments, etc.

By selecting the composition and properties of the matrix and filler, their ratio, filler orientation, it is possible to obtain materials and finished products with the required (preset) combination of operational and technological properties. At present, polymer composite materials are most widely used on the international and Russian markets. High rates of development of the

composites market are determined by a wide range of their properties, which are superior to those of traditional materials. Composite materials are very resistant to external influences, therefore they are suitable for use where resistance to high temperatures, corrosion or heavy loads is needed. Composite materials are excellent electrical insulators for both AC and DC applications. The use of certain fillers makes it possible to obtain composite materials that are resistant to various aggressive media, including the effects of concentrated acids and alkalis. Composites have high mechanical properties, etc.

Ethylene-propylene rubber is currently considered an industrially important product. Rubber products based on it are considered to be resistant to the effects of ozone and heat changes. They also show resistance to the effects of any aggressive environments, while maintaining the good strength and elastic properties of the material.

Rubber products based on ethylene-propylene rubber have high resistance to swelling in water and excellent dielectric properties, which allows them to be used in the cable and electrical industries.

Ethylene-propylene rubber (SKEPT) is well vulcanized with butyl rubber-based rubber compounds and rubbers, improving their technological properties, resistance to heat and frost.

Ethylene-propylene rubbers are extremely incompatible with highly unsaturated rubbers (TK, SKI-3, SKN, SKS, etc.) and their durability is extremely low

due to poor joint vulcanization. One of the biggest disadvantages of ethylene-propylene rubbers is that rubber products based on it have low contact strength with metals and fabrics, ie poor adhesion. These shortcomings hinder the large-scale production and application of ethylene-propylene rubber on an industrial scale.

In order to overcome these shortcomings and increase the widespread use of ethylene-propylene rubber in various industries, it is considered expedient to modify ethylene-propylene rubber with functional group compounds.

For this purpose, the process of modification of ethylene-propylene rubber with alkylaromatic compounds containing functional groups such as chlorine and hydroxy was carried out in the laboratory. Calculated amounts of ethylene-propylene rubber and other components were used for the experiment. 1.2 dichlorophenylethane with functional groups is a clear viscous liquid with a pungent odor. This functional compound was synthesized by the authors in a laboratory facility and its physical and chemical properties were studied.

Experimental part (methodology of the experiment)

Simplified composite materials are materials consisting of two or more components with different chemical composition. In this case, the components are adjacent, but do not form a single whole at the chemical (molecular) level. In the structure of any composite material, a continuous phase or matrix and dispersed phases (one or more) are usually distinguished. A variant is possible in which the material contains several matrices and several dispersed phases in each. One of

the types of such materials are polymer composite materials (PCM), which are currently the most widely used. As the name implies, one or another polymer acts as a matrix in such composite materials. In the case of PCM, the dispersed phase is more often referred to as the filler.

The main reason for the popularity of these composites is that conventional polymers, as well as more traditional materials such as metal or wood, due to their physical properties, can no longer fully meet the needs of the economy, industry and scientific and technological progress. Materials are constantly required, either requiring completely new properties, or increasing the level of existing properties.

As mentioned above, in order to obtain a new environment-resistant polymer-based composite material, we have modified ethylene polyethylene polymer-based rubber with compounds that retain functional groups. As a result, the properties of the new composite materials obtained were studied.

Conducting the experiment. Triple ethylene-propylene rubber is mixed with 1.2 dichlorophenylethane and mechanically modified in the laboratory for 3-4 minutes at a temperature of 40-60°C. On the basis of the material to which the functional group compound is added, the composition is prepared in 25-30 minutes in the composition indicated in Table 1.1.

The prepared composition material is removed from the roller in the form of a flat layer 2-3 mm thick and vulcanized in a hydraulic pressform after storage at room temperature for 4-6 hours.

The obtained composition samples are vulcanized under pressure at a temperature of $153 \pm 10^\circ\text{C}$ for 30 minutes.

Table 1.1

Below shows the composition of the composition based on ethylene-propylene rubber modified with 1.2 dichlorophenylethane.

	The code of the mixture	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
	Name the ingredients									
1.	SKEPT-60	100	97,5	95	92,5	90	85	97	95	92
2.	1.2 dichlorophenylethane	-	2,5	5,0	7,5	10	15	-	-	-
3.	Sulfur	2,0	2,0	2,0	2,0	2,0	2,0	2,0	2,0	2,0
4.	Tiuram	1,5	1,5	1,5	1,5	1,5	1,5	1,5	1,5	1,5
5.	Captaks	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,5
6.	ZnO	5,0	5,0	5,0	5,0	5,0	5,0	5,0	5,0	5,0
7.	Stearic acid	1,0	1,0	1,0	1,0	1,0	1,0	1,0	1,0	1,0
8.	Technical carbon P-234	50,0	50,0	50,5	50,0	50,0	50,0	50,0	50,0	50,0
	Summary	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160

After the vulcanization process is completed, the vulcanized samples are removed from the mold and placed on a table in the laboratory room and stored at room temperature for 5-6 hours. Then the physical and mechanical properties of the composite material obtained by preparing samples from vulcanizates on appropriate equipment (devices) are studied and the obtained results are given in Table 1.2.

Table 1.2.

Physical and mechanical properties of the composite material based on tri-ethylene-propylene rubber 1.2 dichlorophenylethane

	The code of the composition									
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
1.	Tensile strength, MPa	20,1	20,8	21,2	21,4	20,5	18,2	20,9	21,5	20,5
2.	100% tensile strength, MPa	3,1	3,4	4,1	4,5	3,9	3,5	3,7	3,5	3,4
3.	Strength limit at 100% elongation, MPa	13,0	13,603	13,5	14,6	14,1	13,2	13,9	14,0	14,1
4.	Relative elongation, %	381	392	402	408	395	376	387	402	400
5.	Residual deformation, %	14,3	14,1	14,2	14,5	14,7	15,1	14,4	14,3	14,1
6.	Tear resistance, kN / m	34,1	34,9	35,8	35,9	35,2	34,5	41,5	43,5	43,0
7.	Elasticity, %	38,2	39,1	40,3	40,8	39,6	37,2	41,2	41,8	41,5
8.	Strength on TM-2 device, sh.v. 48 hours at 100% temperature	70,3	70,4	70,6	71,2	71,7	72,0	70,5	71,2	71,4
9.	.coefficients of thermal wear over time									
	fmöh. on	0,86	0,87	0,89	0,89	0,88	0,85	0,86	0,88	0,85
	enisb. on elongation	0,57	0,58	0,61	0,58	0,56	0,55	0,58	0,57	0,58
10.	Strength of contact with metal (pol.3) (by tearing), Mpa	1,46	1,63	1,84	2,00	2,55	3,0	3,65	3,72	3,70

Analysis of the physical and mechanical properties of the obtained samples shows that the triple-ethylene-propylene rubber (2.5-7.5) k.h. When modified with 1.2 dichlorophenylethane, all of its physical and mechanical properties improved with respect to triple-ethylene-propylene rubber.

Thus, the tensile strength of the composite material is 4.4 mPa against 3.4, the tensile strength at 300% is 14.9 MPa against 13.1, and the tensile strength is 36.6 kN / m against 33.1.

Triple-ethylene-propylene rubber (3-5) k.h. When modified with 1.2 dichlorophenylethane, the tensile strength is 21.75 MPa versus 20.5 MPa. Conditional stress at 300% elongation is 14.2 MPa against 13.6 MPa, tear resistance is 32.9 kN / m against 44.5 kN / m, metal bond strength is 1.45 MPa against 3.82MPa, heat wear coefficient is 0.76 against Increased to 0.87.

The coefficient of thermal wear increased from 0.85 to 0.89 and the bond strength of the metal increased from 1.42 to 2.75 MPa. As can be seen from Table 1.2, 1.2 dichlorophenylethane and 5 k.h. 1.2 When modified with dichlorophenylethane with triple-ethylene-propylene rubber, their physical and mechanical properties deteriorate.

From the results it can be concluded that triple-ethylene-propylene rubber (2.5-7.5) k.h. The amount can be modified with 1.2 dichlorophenylethane. These indicators coincide with the indicators of rheological properties.

Results and their discussion

1. Modified with triple-ethylene-propylene rubber with 1.2 dichlorophenylethane.

2. The rheological properties of a mixture of triple-ethylene-propylene rubber 1.2 dichlorophenylethane were studied at different voltages in the temperature range (100-190) ° C.

3. It has been shown that the effective viscosity of the alloy of the mixture at 100-150 ° C is high, ie the components in the mixture are connected. At temperatures above 160 ° C, the viscosity decreases, ie either

plasticization takes place or the process of destruction takes place.

4. The dependence of the rate of displacement, displacement voltage of alloys of triple-ethylene-propylene rubber 1.2 dichlorophenylethane mixture in the above temperature ranges was studied and it was shown that the nature of the alloy at (100-150) ° C is Newtonian, and at (170-190) ° C -It's Newton. It can be concluded that the composition obtained on the basis of 1.2 dichlorophenylethane with triple-ethylene-propylene rubber can be processed at a temperature of (150-160)°C.

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